

Service with Conviction

Celebrating My Eleven Years at the
Commonwealth of Learning

Sanjaya Mishra

Introduction

I have never done something like this before. Serving the Commonwealth of Learning (COL) was a dream, and I arrived at COL in 2015 with numerous ideas and a clear vision. Previously, I served as the Director of COL's regional office in New Delhi, and some of the work I did was significant enough to be noted at headquarters. I believe that was one of the reasons I was selected for the position of Education Specialist, eLearning, despite there being many equally or possibly better-suited candidates from around the Commonwealth. I did not write about my accomplishments then. Neither did I prepare documentation of my work at the Indira Gandhi National Open University, nor did I prepare documentation for my work at the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. Despite being a trained professional in organizing information, documenting my work was not a priority for me, which is a pity. With these reflections, I wanted to change that and report on my service at COL, celebrating my contributions. It is not bragging about my work; it is a statement about the vast contributions of COL in the Commonwealth. I have made only a small contribution, alongside similar works by many other colleagues over the years. COL is an excellent example of multilateralism in education. With minimal investments, it helps fill some of the gaps in educational reforms needed across the Commonwealth. While many would attribute the popularity of online learning to COVID-19, COL has been utilizing its limited resources and extensive expertise to promote distance and online learning across the Commonwealth since its inception. A more comprehensive historical analysis would be necessary to fully understand its impact and contributions.

COL, as an organization, has a rotation policy for its professional staff members. Thus, many people would leave after completing just one term of three years. It usually allows staff to serve a maximum of three terms in the same position. Out of the 11 years, I also had the opportunity to serve as Director (Education) for two years.

COL was established to promote the use of technology in education and promote distance education methodologies, thereby expanding access to quality education and training. Thus, the appropriate use of technology in education is the DNA of the organization. Before I joined COL, I had the opportunity to contribute to its 2015-2021 Strategic Plan. The seeds of my key contributions came from this Strategic Plan, which included the stand-alone initiative named 'Technology-Enabled Learning' (TEL) based on my intervention. Before this, there was no existence of this terminology in the discourse of COL. My justification for the change of eLearning (as a cross-cutting theme) to TEL (as an independent initiative) was based on the technological trends and conviction that the technologies that have supported distance education to flourish could be deployed to further expand the quality of education in the conventional education institutions of the Commonwealth by embracing online and blended learning. It is in this context that I would like to acknowledge my modest

contributions. Today, TEL is a common term in day-to-day discourse, not just in COL but throughout the Commonwealth. The use of the term 'enabled' has been justified in a COL publication as:

The word enabled refers to facilitation: learning is made possible by the use of technology. It does not imply the value judgment that the word enhanced necessitates. Technology-Enabled Learning is just about making learning possible, whether that means different ways of serving existing learners or, potentially, providing opportunities for learners who were previously regarded as being “out of reach” — that is, those learners who typically have little to no access to educational opportunities because of a variety of circumstances. (Kirkwood & Price, 2016, p.2)¹

My time at COL could be categorized into three phases: 2015-2019 (pre-pandemic), 2020-2021 (during the pandemic), and 2022-2025 (post-pandemic). The period categorization is based on the developments and progress. But I am not going to use the pandemic as the reference point for celebration. Instead, I will use thematic grouping and narrative to highlight key points of celebration.

Understanding the Status of ICT in Education

Early in 2015, I realized the importance of data and having authentic information to advise governments. Especially, it was necessary to conduct a stocktaking of the progress of ICT in Education in Commonwealth countries. Thus, we commissioned four reports on the topic, which provided us with a better understanding of regional as well as country-level innovations, projects, and policies. Similar studies/reports must be conducted regularly on various aspects of COL's work to inform the development of evidence-based strategies.

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Leadership in OER

COL has been a pioneer in promoting open educational resources (OER). Sharing educational resources is a key function enshrined in the Memorandum of Understanding of the organization. Thus, promoting OER has become an integral part of its activities. In 2011, it became the first intergovernmental organization to adopt an open licensing policy, releasing its works under a CC BY-SA license. One of the earliest projects I undertook at COL was organizing the Open Textbook Forum for Caribbean countries in October 2015. The Hewlett Foundation supported the project. Promoting OER work at the national level became part of my portfolio, and I worked closely with colleagues at UNESCO and other stakeholders. In 2016, we published an edited book on OER, highlighting the progress of OER in several countries. In 2016-2017, with the support of the Hewlett Foundation, COL organized several regional consultations on OER leading up to the second World OER Congress held in Slovenia. I led the regional consultation in Asia and also prepared the Report on OER and the action plan. Both these documents formed the basis of the final OER Action Plan adopted by the Congress. I also started a short course on OER offered on the COL's Moodle platform, which later became a very popular course and an independent platform supporting the OER movement worldwide. In 2019, UNESCO adopted the OER Recommendation, and I collaborated with UNESCO to develop policy guidelines for OER. Over the years, COL has become a key destination for information on OER, and I also had the opportunity to work with several governments in developing OER policies. Strategically, we also positioned COL's work on ICT in education to include OER policy. Two notable examples of OER policy development that I would like to highlight are those of Malaysia and Mauritius.

Digital Education Leadership

COL is one of the leading organizations to recognize the importance of digital education. In 2015, we began collaborating with the University of Cape Town and several international experts to develop a framework for digital education leadership. This effort resulted in the creation of seven modules, which were subsequently integrated into an online platform to scale digital education leadership training. The

Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action (C-DELTA) platform² was a finalist in the prestigious Berlin Falling Wall 2020 and received the Brandon Hall Excellence in Learning Gold Award 2021. The platform has 40,044 registrations and 19,050 certificates issued as of November 19, 2025. The platform has been designed to provide self-learning opportunities for teachers and students in secondary education and beyond.

Transition to Online Learning

Covid-19 dealt a devastating blow to humanity, and all our activities had to come to a halt in March 2020. As a resilient organization, we responded quickly by releasing guidelines to help governments and institutions transition to online learning. I conducted/participated in 43 webinars in 2020-21. I was scheduled to travel to Malaysia in April 2020 to conduct a workshop, but we quickly transformed it into a series of webinar-based training sessions. The 12-part webinar series³ on the design and development of massive open online courses (MOOCs), developed specifically for Universiti Malaysia Sabah (UMS), was also made available to others. The level of engagement was high, and 70 participants, the majority of whom were from the UMS, completed the course. We also provided certificates and online badges to the successful participants. UMS also developed and delivered a MOOC on Bio-Risk Management, which was very appropriate at that time. A key lesson during the COVID-19 period was the poor use of Zoom video conferencing sessions. Thus, I also developed a video on how to conduct effective webinars.⁴ During COVID-19, Prof

Tony Bates supported COL in developing 12 videos⁵ around his textbook on 'Teaching in a Digital Age.' We adopted the textbook and around his textbook on 'Teaching in a Digital Age.' We adopted the textbook and the videos to develop a self-learning course on COL's Moodle platform. The

videos were recorded remotely by me using Zoom. We are ever grateful to Prof. Bates for the support provided. Several persons across the Commonwealth have completed the course.

COLCommons: A Short Course Platform

During the COVID-19 pandemic, as the majority of our work transitioned to online support for partner institutions and governments, an internal discussion ensued on how to optimize our presence and activities. At that time, we already had the LearnOER platform offering self-learning on ‘Understanding OER.’ We quickly converted the platform into a multi-course platform called COLCommons.org.⁶ We adapted an open textbook on BC Campus to develop a course on Universal Design for Learning. We commissioned other scholars to create more courses. Currently, there

are 13 short courses, including one written by me, titled ‘Preparing Distance Learning Material’. Over the years, the platform has received seven Innovation Excellence Awards from Brandon Hall. As of November 19, 2025, the platform had 46,017 registrations, 72,661 enrolments, and 39,772

certificates issued. The platform has become a key source of support for training in partner institutions across COL initiatives.

Maturation of TEL Model

As I began with the TEL initiative, institutional adoption of TEL became a key component of our work, grounded in a strong theory of change and research evidence from different parts of the world. I was aware that the research literature on TEL from Commonwealth countries is limited, and promoting TEL adoption at scale would require a more evidence-based and evidence-informed approach. The TEL implementation model is based on the Policy-Capacity-Technology triangle.⁷ Lack of any of these three in an institution or if any of these is ineffective, the implementation may not have an impact or bring change. Understanding the budget constraints and the need to allow time for adopting the required changes at the partner institutions, we planned a phased approach to TEL implementation, covering a range of activities over a 2–3-year time period. Several institutions in the Commonwealth have

implemented TEL by adopting the COL model. As our focus was also on building evidence for effective TEL implementation, we conducted baseline

studies and impact evaluations to inform our efforts. A summary of research conducted at some partner institutions is synthesized in a COL publication.⁸ COL is a capacity builder, and the COL TEL model has a strong focus on capacity building for teachers. During the COVID-19 pandemic, capacity-building activities were conducted online using COL's Moodle platform for TEL. As such, the COL TEL implementation model comprises several tools and guidelines, including a handbook, survey tools for baseline studies, workshop templates for capacity building, a guidebook on blended learning⁹, a tool to assess the quality of blended courses, and a toolkit for benchmarking TEL. With the advent of AI in teaching and learning, we have also developed guidelines on AI policy development.¹⁰ Additionally, we created a Community of Practice (CoP) for partner institutions to collaborate and share lessons learned. The platform-based CoP did not receive active engagement, despite having over 5,000 registrations. After several attempts, it was closed in 2023. Some of the partner institutions that initiated the TEL implementation journey before COVID-19 greatly benefited from the COL support, as the capacities developed enabled them to transition to online learning quickly.

As part of the TEL implementation, we also collaborated with Athabasca University in Canada to develop a range of MOOCs related to various topics. We offered these globally to adopt best practices in integrating ICTs in teaching and learning. The TEL initiative offered 22 MOOCs reaching over 30,000 participants. As a result of our work, we have developed new approaches to evaluating MOOCs.¹¹ A study on the participant experience of the TEL MOOCs for professional development of teachers argued for a new strategy for assessing completion rate in MOOCs:

There is no sound reason, that we are aware of, to calculate MOOC success using registration numbers for a course. MOOC reports should at a minimum be using active learners as the basis for their completion calculations. We define active learners as those who have signed into the course space at least one time (Ostashewski & Cleveland-Innes, 2022, p.57)¹²

Accordingly, the TEL MOOCs had a completion rate of above 70% and demonstrated value for money, which is a core principle of COL's engagement in various areas and countries.

ICT Skills Development

In the Strategic Plan 2015-2021, the TEL initiative had a minor focus on developing advanced ICT skills. In order to streamline this activity, we collaborated with six open universities in the Commonwealth to develop two programmes on Mobile Application Development and Web Application Development. The advanced ICT skills development project was further expanded to other partner institutions to create OER on job-oriented courses.¹³ We developed several courses in partnership with

different institutions, and an estimate revealed that the download and use of the courses developed could have saved over 8 million USD by December 2019.¹⁴ The ICT Skill development project also adopted many different routes to utilize the courses developed. One significant success story is the COL's support to Kampabits, Uganda, where marginalized, unemployed youth (both boys and girls) from the slums of Kampala were trained to become skilled designers and programmers. An evaluation of the project revealed that every dollar spent on this project resulted in \$3.48 value.¹⁵ The ICT skills development project was stopped after the mid-term evaluation of the Strategic Plan 2021-2027, as the Kampabits project was conducted mainly face-to-face. Nevertheless, the number of courses developed and the capacity building for OER and instructional design facilitated in the partner institutions were significant, enabling these institutions to leverage them in other disciplines and areas.

Contributions to PCF

The Pan-Commonwealth Forum on Open Learning is a key event organized by COL every three years since 1999. I had the opportunity to participate in PCF in Durban, London, and Abuja before joining COL. I served as co-chair for the PCF Programme at PCF8 (Kuala Lumpur) and PCF9 (Edinburgh), and as a member of the PCF10 (Calgary) programme team. I also contributed as a peer reviewer for PCF11 (Gaborone). For PCF8, PCF9, and PCF10, I assisted the COL President with the presentations by coordinating with the programme manager and rapporteurs. The PCFs have brought together experts from around the Commonwealth and beyond, and especially provided COL partners with a platform to share their experiences, innovations, and lessons learned.

CEMBA/CEMPA

The Commonwealth Executive MBA/MPA programme has been a notable example of institutional collaboration facilitated by COL, pooling resources to offer high-quality programmes across the Commonwealth. Initially, the learning materials of the programme were sourced from select institutions in Asia, which voluntarily contributed the materials to a pool for use by partners through a coordinating mechanism led by COL. Over time, these learning materials needed revision. As Director (Education), I guided the revision process of the courses of the CEMBA programme to integrate available OER.

Focus on ODL

As Director (Education), my focus was to bring back discourse as well as the focus of COL activities around open and distance learning (ODL). For all the activities we asked, is it relevant to ODL? Should COL be doing this or doing that? If COL is not

doing x, who else could do that activity? In the process, we also held an internal workshop on ODL to discuss and accommodate new developments, as well as how we can develop strategies/ policies supporting ODL by working with governments to increase access to quality education and training in the post-pandemic world. Bringing back discussions around ODL within COL is something I feel pleased about, although there is still a lot more to be done.

At a time when many different players are utilizing distance and online learning, COL must lead from the front to guide Commonwealth countries in doing the right things, in the right way, to ensure quality, empower people, and support sustainable development.

Journal of Learning for Development

It is very satisfying to see that the Journal of Learning for Development (JL4D) has emerged as a scholarly journal in the ODL field. The publication of the Journal started with the support of external consultants in 2014. However, on my arrival at COL Headquarters, the task of managing the Journal was handed over to me with a tiny budget for copyediting. Today, the Journal has more than three times the budget it had up to 2020, and it receives a large number of submissions. In the early days of the Journal, we had to struggle to get good papers from scholars. One of the reasons cited by many was that the Journal was not listed in Scopus or Web of Science. While indexing is not a measure of a journal's quality, it is a norm in the research community. The Journal is now listed on Scopus as well as the Directory of Open Access Journals. The h-index of the Journal on Google Scholar is increasing. A significant reason is that journal papers are also available on ERIC and OASIS, in addition to being open access on the journal platform. These days, the waiting period for publication in JL4D is nearly one year. I have personally nurtured the publication of the Journal and its book reviews section, and I hope the Journal will continue to grow and support scholars from the developing Commonwealth.

Scholarly Contributions

During my tenure at COL, I have been involved in several scholarly activities, including writing chapters, journal papers, making presentations at conferences and seminars, and conducting workshops at partner institutions. I also played an essential role in the development of several COL publications. Some of the COL publications in which I played a role (either as author, editor, or coordinator) are included in Annex 1. Additionally, Annex 2 provides a list of presentations, and Annex 3 details the workshops conducted over the years. As I look back, I feel delighted with these contributions, which do not list many of my academic achievements that I also undertook beyond COL duties. Annex 4 includes some book chapters and peer-reviewed journal papers related to COL works.

International Collaborations

I had the privilege of collaborating with several international organizations during my service at COL. I wrote two significant grant proposals for the Hewlett Foundation – one for the regional consultations on OER and the Global report for the second World OER Congress, and the second on OER for skills development. In collaboration with the UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education and the Beijing Normal University, I prepared a report on smart education strategies for teaching and learning.[16] In collaboration with the UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning, we developed a publication and a course on open and distance learning for adult education professionals. I had close cooperation with UNESCO’s education sector and also represented COL at the UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition. In addition, I contributed to discussions with organizations like the Arab League of Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization (ALECSO), Hamdan Bin Mohammed Smart University (for benchmarking of the Benchmarking Framework for Online, Open, Smart, and Technology-Enhanced Higher Education, and the Quality Stackable Education), Network of Open Organizations, and Global Smart Education Network. Collaboration is key to supporting educational development work.

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Internal Process Development and Quality

I continuously strived for internal efficiency and advocated for not duplicating our work, reviewing what we have done in the past before taking any future steps. Such an approach required several standard tools, including policy tracking and a course development registry. To ensure the quality assurance of publications, I also contributed to the peer review process as needed. I had the privilege to work with colleagues to develop the Micro-credential Framework for the Commonwealth. This is a significant collaborative work within COL, as well as outside. Towards the end of my tenure at COL, I also facilitated a workshop on case study development for the professional staff to highlight the success stories, and support monitoring and evaluation. This workshop was based on my experience of developing six case studies listed towards the end of Annex-1.

Countries and Institutions Supported

During my service at COL, I had the opportunity to serve (not necessarily travelled): Antigua and Barbuda, The Bahamas, Bangladesh, Belize, Botswana, Cameroon, Canada, Fiji, Guyana, India, Kenya, Malaysia, Malawi, Maldives, Malta, Mauritius, Nigeria, Pakistan, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Seychelles, South Africa, Sri Lanka, St. Lucia, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zambia. I also had interactions with officials from many other countries in the Commonwealth and beyond. I worked with over 50 institutions in these countries. The list of institutions supported through various activities is in Annex 5.

For all the activities we asked, is it relevant to ODL? Should COL be doing this or doing that? If COL is not doing x, who else could do that activity?

Concluding Observations

There are two options to review our work. First, a critical perspective, and second, an appreciative inquiry. We are all smart in hindsight, and our mind provides us with a whole lot of negative points about how things could have been done better. An appreciative frame requires a more deliberate approach to find ways to celebrate and synthesize lessons that others can follow. While I have many stories to share about my experiences at COL, this documentation focuses on my work, contributions, and achievements that I would like to remember and celebrate. I have led many activities described in this document. However, most of the works are the result of collaboration. For example, the publication of a report requires support from the Communication team members and also external peer reviewers. I had the privilege of a vast network of people outside the organization, as well as several individuals within COL who supported me. I am personally thankful to each one of them. I have acknowledged some of the non-COL collaborators/ consultants at the end, while I may have missed many. However, I would specially recognize the support received from two important COL people. First, I would like to thank Prof. Asha Kanwar for bringing me to COL headquarters and for believing in my convictions about ODL for development. Second, I would like to thank Prof. Peter Scott for listening to me during the final years of my tenure, while several changes were in progress under his leadership.

If you have reached the end of this document, thank you for taking the time to read it. Please let me know if I can assist you in the future.

Annex 1: List of Major Publications/Reports Contributed by Sanjaya Mishra at COL

2015

1. Understanding Open Educational Resources <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1013>
2. Tablets for Teaching and Learning: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1012>
3. Large-Scale, Government-Supported Educational Tablet Initiatives <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/809>
4. A Guide to Virtual Universities for Policy-Makers <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1723>
5. Educational App Development Toolkit for Teachers and Learners <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1729>
6. Technology-Enabled Learning in the Commonwealth Caribbean Countries: A Baseline Study <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/1210>
7. A Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning in the Commonwealth Pacific Island Countries: Report <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/1738>
8. A Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning in the Asian Commonwealth <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/1208>
9. A Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning in the African and Mediterranean Countries of the Commonwealth: Report <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/1674>

2016

10. Curriculum for Digital Education Leadership: A Concept Paper <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2442>
11. Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation Handbook <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2363>
12. Guidelines for Quality Assurance and Accreditation of MOOCs <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2362>
13. Open Educational Resources: Policy, Costs and Transformation <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2306>
14. Open Educational Resources in the Commonwealth 2016 <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2441>
15. Quality in MOOCs: Surveying the Terrain <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2352>
16. Guide to Developing Open Textbooks <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2390>
17. Open Educational Resources in the Commonwealth 2016 <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2441>
18. Open Educational Resources Policy for Higher Education in Nigeria <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2798>
19. Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning: Course Materials <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2765>
20. The Report of Baseline Study: ICT-based Learning <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2690>

2017

21. Open Universities in the Commonwealth: At a Glance <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2786>
22. Open Educational Resources: Global Report 2017 <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2788>
23. Open Educational Resources: From Commitment to Action <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2789>
24. Promoting Use and Contribution of Open Educational Resources <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2659>
25. Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning: Course Materials <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2765>
26. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2760>

27. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at the National University of Samoa <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2755>
28. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning in Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2751>
- 2018
29. Gender and ICT: Meta-Analysis and Systematic Review <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3089>
30. Guide to Blended Learning <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3095>
31. Can Technology Solve the Problems of Higher Education? <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2983>
32. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 2) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2970>
33. Report on the Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3096>
34. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Malaysia Sabah <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2974>
35. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Uganda Management Institute <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2855>
36. Student Guide to Effective Learning Using Information and Communication Technologies <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3093>
- 2019
37. Guidelines on the Development of Open Educational Resources Policies <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3455>
38. Benchmarking Toolkit for Technology-Enabled Learning <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3217>
39. Pedagogical Innovations for Technology-Enabled Learning <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3201>
40. Designing and Implementing Micro-Credentials: A Guide for Practitioners <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3279>
41. Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action: An Evaluation <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3478>
42. Learners' Access to Educational Materials in Select Institutions within the Commonwealth <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3479>
43. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 3) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3134>
44. Evaluating Long-term MOOC Impact: A Case Study of TEL MOOC <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3347>
45. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3220>
46. Report on the Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at the University of Papua New Guinea <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3214>
47. The Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Malaysia Sabah <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3483>
48. The Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3119>
49. Learning with Technology: A Student Guide <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3200>
50. The Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at the National University of Samoa <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3196>
51. ICT for Youth Employability: Evaluation Report. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3199>
- 2020
52. Technology-Enabled Learning: Policy, Pedagogy and Practice <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3655>

53. Guidelines on Distance Education during COVID-19 <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3576>
54. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3664>
55. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Malaysia Sabah <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3736>
56. Conducting an Effective Webinar Session <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HWnYUvKV5NQ>
57. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 6) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3667>
58. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 5) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3663>
59. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 4) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3493>
60. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 7) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3745>
61. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3664>
62. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP MOOC4) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3746>
63. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP MOOC 2 and 3) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3666>
64. Report on the Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at Kaimosi Friends University College <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3496>
65. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Kibabii University <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3685>
66. Report on the Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at Antigua State College <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3662>
67. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Malaysia Sabah <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3736>
68. The Impact of Blended Learning at the Uganda Management Institute <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3625>

2021

69. Guidelines on Open and Distance Learning for Youth and Adult Literacy <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3965>
70. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 10) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4010>
71. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 9) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3879>
72. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL MOOC 8) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3868>
73. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP MOOC6) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3892>
74. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP MOOC5) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3884>
75. Learning to Learn Online: Course Materials <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3737>
76. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Learning to Learn Online (LTLO MOOC) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3913>
77. Report on the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Model Institute of Education and Research <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3891>
78. The Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3925>

79. Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning on Student Learning Experiences and Teacher Pedagogic Practices at The University of Papua New Guinea
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3886>
80. Blended Course Experience at Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3780>
81. Introduction to Social Media Marketing: Course Material <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3796>
82. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Social Media Marketing (ISMM) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4005>
83. Computational Thinking for Teachers <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3882>
84. Universal Design for Learning <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3881>
85. Learning Analytics: A Primer <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3883>
86. Introduction to microlearning <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3877>

2022

87. Smart Education Strategies for Teaching and Learning: Critical Analytical Framework and Case Studies <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4464>
88. Transforming Education for Climate Action: Report to Commonwealth Ministers of Education <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4068>
89. Technology Application in Teaching and Learning: Second-Order Review of Meta-analyses <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4069>
90. Participant Experience in an Inquiry-Based Massive Open Online Course
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4132>
91. Open Educational Resources in the Commonwealth 2021 <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4009>
92. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLP MOOC7)
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4050>
93. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Leading Change in Teaching and Learning for a Digital World <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4060>
94. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at Nakuru Training Institute <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4645>
95. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at Alupe University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4990>
96. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4471>
97. Institutional Surveys on Open Educational Resources at Fiji National University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4934>
98. The Impact of Blended Learning at the Fiji National University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4749>
99. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4472>
100. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4477>
101. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4476>
102. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Putra Malaysia
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4474>
103. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Malaya
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4473>
104. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4475>
105. Blended Course Experience at Kibabii University <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4512>
106. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Introduction to Social Media Marketing-2 (ISMM2) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4787>

107. Motivating and Supporting Online Learners <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4481>
 108. Quality Assurance of Blended and Online Learning <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4484>
- 2023
109. Open Universities in the Commonwealth: At a Glance (2nd ed.)
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5216>
 110. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLPMOOC8)
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5346>
 111. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Designing for Communities of Inquiry in Online Courses <https://oasis.colvee.org/handle/123456789/5365>
 112. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Designing for Communities of Inquiry in Online Courses (DCoIMOOC2) <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5508>
 113. Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at the Mahatma Gandhi Institute
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5376>
 114. Report on the Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at the Mauritius Institute of Education <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5256>
 115. Baseline Study of Technology-Enabled Learning at the National Institute of Education, Maldives <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5379>
 116. Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at the University of Kabianga
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5442>
 117. Report of the Baseline Study on Technology-Enabled Learning at the Islamic University of Maldives <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5257>
 118. Technology-Enabled Learning at the Four Public Higher Education Institutions of Mauritius
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5359>
 119. Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning at MIER <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5227>
 120. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5225>
 121. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Kibabii University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5349>
 122. Blended Learning Course Experience at Kaimosi Friends University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5475>
 123. Learning Design for Emerging Learning Environments <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5248>
 124. Machine Learning for Everyone <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5366>
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125. Policy and Practice of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Learning at Post-secondary Educational Institutions in the Commonwealth <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5605>
 126. Developing Policy Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence in Post-secondary Institutions
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5615>
 127. Preparing Distance Learning Materials <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5616>
 128. Report of the Massive Open Online Course on Blended Learning Practice (BLPMOOC9)
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5602>
 129. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at MIER College of Education
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5603>
 130. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at International Islamic University Malaysia <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5514>
 131. Report of the Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Universiti Sains Malaysia
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5515>
 132. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at University of Kabianga
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5690>
 133. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at Alupe University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5689>

134. The Impact of Technology-Enabled Learning at Alupe University
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5575>

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135. Technology-Enabled Learning in the Commonwealth Countries: A Research Synthesis
<http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5696>
136. Blended Learning Course Experiences in Higher Education Institutions in Mauritius
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5712>
137. Understanding User Satisfaction and Experience with C-DELTA
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5735>
138. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the University of Technology, Mauritius
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5741>
139. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the University of Mauritius
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5740>
140. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the Université des Mascareignes
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5739>
141. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the Open University of Mauritius
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5738>
142. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the Mauritius Institute of Education
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5737>
143. Benchmarking of Technology-Enabled Learning at the Mahatma Gandhi Institute
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5736>
144. Towards a Micro-credential Framework for the Commonwealth
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5742>
145. Understanding User Satisfaction and Experience with COLCommons
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5964>
146. TEL Case Study: Integrating Technology into Teaching and Learning: Lessons from JOOUST. <https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5969>
147. TEL Case Study: Mainstreaming Technology-Enabled Learning: Strategies from UMS.
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5968>
148. TEL Case Study: Guiding Change: Mainstreaming Technology-Enabled Learning through a National Agency. <https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5967>
149. TEL Case Study: Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at MIER: A Transformative Journey. <https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5966>
150. TEL Case Study: Technology-Enabled Learning at the National University of Samoa.
<https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5970>
151. TEL Case Study: Digital Education Leadership Training in South Africa: Learning from SchoolNet. <https://hdl.handle.net/11599/5971>

Annex 2: Presentations by Dr Sanjaya Mishra During Service at COL

1. Mishra, S. (2025). Ten Dimensions of Digital Transformation in Higher Education. Keynote address at the DX 2025: Global Conference on Digital Transformation in Higher Education, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia on 27 October 2025. <https://zenodo.org/records/17457632>
2. Mishra, S. (2025). Quality in Digital Education: What, Why and How. Lecture delivered online at the Ghana Communication Technology University on July 9, 2025. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dSMP0qpII_E
3. Mishra, S. (2024). Models of Blended Learning: Presentation by Dr Sanjaya Mishra, Education Specialist (Technology-Enabled Learning) at the North Zone Vice Chancellors' meeting organised by the Association of Indian Universities at Graphic Era Hill University, Dehradun, India on November 5, 2024. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5665>
4. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2023). Future of Open Universities: Keynote at the AAOU 36th Annual Conference, Istanbul, Turkey, on 28 September 2023. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5455>
5. Mishra, S. (2023). Flexible Digital Learning, Micro-Credentialing and Assessment Practices in the Commonwealth: Online keynote presentation delivered at the 48th International Association for Educational Assessment (IAEA) Conference in Kingston, Jamaica, on 25 September 2023. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5454>
6. Mishra, S. (2023). Supporting Digital Transformation to Build Resilience: COL Experience: Presented at the UNESCO Global SIDS Dialogue Series on 'Digital transformation in SIDS for building Resilience and Openness to external shocks including the impact of COVID-19 in education systems', 4-5 April 2023, UNESCO, Paris. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5285>
7. Mishra, S. (2023). Applying Benchmarking for Better Performance of Open Universities: Introductory remarks at the UNESCO IITE Webinar Series on Harnessing Technology to Transform Education held on 21 March 2023. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5258>
8. Mishra, S. (2023). Towards Open University of Kenya: Models and Lessons from the Commonwealth. Presented at the planning meeting organised by the Ministry of Education, Kenya on 5 March 2023. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5249>
9. Mishra, S. (2023). Digital Education: Unlocking the Potential of Every Mind. Presented at the Caribbean Community (CARICOM) Digital Skills Taskforce Webinar organised by CARICOM and UNESCO, held in Kingston, Jamaica on 2 March 2023. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5247>
10. Mishra, S. (2022). The Politics of Quality Assurance in Blended and Online Learning: Who are the Stakeholders. Presented at the International Conference on Teaching, Assessment, and Learning in the Digital Age in Durban, South Africa, on 1 December 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4788>
11. Mishra, S. (2022). Flexible Learning in a Digital Age: Towards a Micro-credential Framework. Presented at the 2nd Ministerial Summit of the Caribbean Examination Council (CXC), St George's, Grenada, on 11 November 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4693>
12. Mishra, S. (2022). Smart Education Strategies for Teaching and Learning. Presented at the Global Smart Education Conference organised by the Beijing University, China on 20 August 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4378>
13. Mishra, S., & Ferreira, F. (2022). Workforce Recovery Programme. Virtually presented at the 38th Commonwealth Diplomat's Induction Programme, London, United Kingdom, 8 March 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4023>
14. Mishra, S. (2022). Virtual University for Small States of the Commonwealth: Mechanisms and Lessons: Virtually presented at the Consultation on Renewal of UCSIS with Higher Education Institutions in Small Island States, organised by UNESCO, on 15 February 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4012>

15. Mishra, S. (2022). Open Educational Resources: Status and Trends: A virtual presentation and interaction with the students of Indiana University, Bloomington on February 14, 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4013>
16. Mishra, S. (2021). Supporting Learners in Distance and Online Learning: Lessons for Educators. Foundation Day Lecture at the Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University, India on 11 December 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/4003>
17. Mishra, S. (2021). Media and Learning: Lessons for Educators. Presentation delivered by at the Webinar on “Media and Learning: Challenges and Opportunities” organised by the Central Institute of Educational Technology, National Council of Educational Research and Training, India on 1 September 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3921>
18. Mishra, S. (2021). Integrating Open Educational Resources in Blended Courses. Presentation delivered at a workshop held at the Centre for Educational Excellence, Simon Fraser University, Canada on 25 August 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3919>
19. Mishra, S. (2021). Implementing the UNESCO OER Recommendation: COL Experiences. Presentation at the online panel discussion during Annual Conference of the Asian Association of Open Universities held at Open University of Sri Lanka on 3 June 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3872>
20. Mishra, S. (2021). Measuring Institutional Readiness for Flexibility in Teaching and Learning: The Ten Indicators. Keynote Presentation at the ICDE 2021 Leadership Summit, 9 April 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3781>
21. Mishra, S. (2021). Online Education: A catalyst for reforming higher education. Lecture at a workshop organised by Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, India on March 6, 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3752>
22. Mishra, S. (2021). Alternative Assessment Strategies for eLearning. Lecture to MPhil students of University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Pakistan on January 3, 2021. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3753>
23. Mishra, S. (2020). Chaired a session at the Webinar for 100 Years of Media Education organised by Institute of International Journalism, Ohio University, USA; Dr Anamika Ray Memorial Trust, Guwahati, India and Institute of Media Studies and Research, Mysore, India on December 20, 2020.
24. Mishra, S. (2020). “Communication Principles in Implementing Technology-Enabled Learning” at the International Webinar organised by the Indonesian Communication Scholars Association on December 10, 2020.
25. Mishra, S. (2020). Participated in the OUSL Book Launch discussion on “Pathways to Open Educational Practices” on November 30, 2020.
26. Mishra, S. (2020). “Promoting Digital Education in the Commonwealth”, Invited presentation by Dr. Sanjaya Mishra, Education Specialist: eLearning at the European Online and Distance Learning Week organised by the European Distance and E-Learning Network on 2 November 2020. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3692>
27. Mishra, S. (2020). “Alternative assessment strategies for authentic Learning” at the Open University of Sri Lanka Faculty Webinar on October 22, 2020.
28. Mishra, S. (2020). “Designing Student Engagements in Technology-Enabled Learning” at the Webinar “World Teachers Day 2020 and our Challenges” organised by the Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Digital University, Bangladesh on October 13, 2020.
29. Mishra, S. (2020). “Open Educational Resources” at the International Online Webinar on “New Spaces & Emerging Dialogues: Fresh Perspectives on Teaching/Learning of Foreign Languages” organised by School of Foreign Languages, Indira Gandhi National Open University, India on October 1, 2020.
30. Mishra, S. (2020). “MOOCs, e-Content Development and Open Educational Resources”. Keynote address at the National Webinar on at Sambalpur University, India on 7 September 2020. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3659>

31. Mishra, S. (2020). Participated as a panelist on “The Future of Education is Open” organised by Creative Commons India on August 29, 2020.
32. Mishra, S. (2020). “Designing and Delivering Online Learning” at the Webinar Online Learning & Teaching: Issues & Trends organised by the Punjab University, India on June 19, 2020.
33. Mishra, S. (2020). “Three Myths of Technology-Enabled Learning” at the Webinar on Digital Technology for TVET: Possibilities and Challenges organised by the Ambedkar University, India on May 29, 2020.
34. Mishra, S. (2020). “Understanding Open Educational Resources” at the Faculty training programme organised by the Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Kenya on May 12, 2020
35. Mishra, S. (2020). “OER4COVID initiative of COL” at the Webinar on” Advancing Open Educational Practice in line with UNESCO OER Recommendations during COVID-19 Pandemic”, organised by the Smart Learning Institute of Beijing Normal University (SLIBNU), UNESCO INRULED and UNESCO IITE on May 8, 2020.
36. Mishra, S. (2020). “Rethinking student assessment and evaluation” at the Online International Conference on Teaching-Learning in the Time of Pandemic: Role of Online Learning organised by KK Handiqui State Open University, India on April 22, 2020.
37. Mishra, S. (2020). “COL’s interventions on OER during COVID-19” at the Online Training Session organised by Arab League Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization on April 11, 2020.
38. Perris, K., and Mishra, S. (2020). “Supporting remote teaching and learning during COVID-19” at Webinar organised by eCampus Ontario on April 9, 2020.
39. Mishra, S. (2020). Africa and Europe consultation webinars for OER4COVID initiative with OER Foundation on April 9, 2020. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M_aK7eKfPHM
40. Mishra, S. (2020). Asia, Pacific and the Caribbean consultation webinars for OER4COVID initiative with OER Foundation on April 8, 2020. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dh-Ec5wKQb0>
41. Mishra, S. (2020). Participated in the “Silver Lining for Learning”, Episode 4, as one of the guests to speak about COL’s work on April 11, 2020. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E-oNumJp84o>
42. Mishra, S. (2020). Participated in a live panel discussion virtually for India Ahead News Channel in India on April 14, 2020. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i-ldsZTYes0>
43. Mishra, S. (2019). Rethinking Openness: Experiences from the Commonwealth. Keynote address delivered online by Dr Sanjaya Mishra, Education Specialist: eLearning on December 2, 2019 at the XXVII International Conference on Distance Education, Guadalajara, Mexico. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3477>
44. Ostashewski, Nathaniel, Wilton, Dan, Cleveland-Innes, Martha, & Mishra, Sanjaya (2019). Supporting Open Education Resource qualification and creation: The TEL MOOC Case, Paper presented at the 9th Pan-Commonwealth Forum on Open Learning at Edinburgh from 9-12 September 2019. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3344>
45. Kanwar, A. & Mishra, S. (2019). Learners Our Common Wealth: Towards Lifelong Learning for All, Presented by Professor Asha Kanwar, President & CEO, Commonwealth of Learning at the Council for Education in the Commonwealth Annual Conference 21 to 23 May 2019. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3192>.
46. Mishra, S. (2019). Open Educational Resources in the Pacific. Public Lecture by Dr. Sanjaya Mishra, Education Specialist, eLearning, Commonwealth of Learning at Fiji National University, Fiji on 11 March, 2019 and at University of Papua New Guinea on 15 March 2019. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3128>
47. Kanwar, A., Carr, A., Balasubramanian, K., & Mishra, S. (2019). Achieving Lifelong Learning for All: Where are We Now? What Next? Presented by Professor Asha Kanwar, President & CEO, Commonwealth of Learning at the ICDE Lillehammer Lifelong Learning Summit 2019, 11 February 2019. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3116>

48. Kanwar, A., Mishra, S., & Cheng, R. (2018). Open Educational Practices and Quality Assurance: Leaving No One Behind! Presented by Professor Asha Kanwar, President & CEO, Commonwealth of Learning, at the International Conference on Open and Distance e-Learning (ICODEL), 26 November 2018. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3097>
49. Ashman, M., Mishra, S., Nieves, C. M., O'Brien, J., & Sprout, B. (2018, October 24). Open But Not Free: Invisible Labour in Open Scholarship [O]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14288/1.0373485>
50. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2018). Human Resource Development and Lifelong Learning for Open Universities: Presented by Professor Asha Kanwar, President & CEO, Commonwealth of Learning, at the 32nd Annual Conference of the Asian Association of Open Universities, 26 October 2018. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3090>
51. Ostashewski, N., Wilton, D., Cleveland-Innes, M. & Mishra, S. (2018). Learner analytics as a tool for guiding instruction: Identifying High Interest Discussion Topics in a MOOC. In *Proceedings of E-Learn: World Conference on E-Learning in Corporate, Government, Healthcare, and Higher Education* (pp. 526-529). Las Vegas, NV, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/185003/>
52. Mishra, S. (2018). Promoting Digital Education Leadership for Lifelong Learning, Keynote presentation at eLearning Korea 2018 in Seoul, September 14, 2018.
53. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2018). Global Trends in OER: What is the Future?: Presented by Professor Asha Kanwar at the International Conference on Open and Innovative Education (ICOIE), Hong Kong SAR, 4 July 2018. Co-written with Dr Sanjaya Mishra, COL. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3053>
54. Ostashewski, N., Cleveland-Innes, M., Mishra, S., & Wilton, D. (2018). Supporting OER creation as a professional development outcome: The Technology-Enabled Learning MOOC. In *Proceedings of the SITE 2018*, Washington, D.C., United States, March 26-30, 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/182751/>
55. Mishra, S. (2018). Keynote Address: Indian Higher Education: Role of Library Professionals. Presented at the National Seminar on "Recent Trends and Practices in Librarianship," 24 March 2018, Sambalpur University, Burla, India. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2938>
56. Mishra, S. (2018). Key Issues in Technology-Enabled Learning: Policy Considerations. Presented at the Workshop on Policy Development for Technology-Enabled Learning, 19 March 2018, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2940>
57. Mishra, S. (2018). Research Trends in Educational Technology: Some Observations. Lecture delivered at the SNDT Women's University, Mumbai, India, on 16 March 2018. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2939>
58. Kanwar, A., Abeywardena, I., & Mishra, S. (2018). Smart OER: Bridges for Sustainable Education. Presented at Innovation Arabia 11, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 11 March 2018. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2933>
59. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2018). Higher Education in an Age of Disruption. Presented by Prof. Asha Kanwar at Innovation Arabia 11, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 11 March 2018. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2930>
60. Kanwar, A., Abeywardena, I., & Mishra, S. (2017). Accessible OER: Where to start?. *Presented at the 6th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology and Accessibility, 20 December 2017, Muscat, Sultanate of Oman.* Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2829>
61. Kanwar, A., Balasubramanian, K., & Mishra, S. (2017). Can Open Learning Transform Society? *Presented at the International Conference on Developmental Interventions and Open Learning for Empowering and Transforming Society, 16-17 December 2017, Guwahati, India.* Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2828>
62. Cleveland-Innes, M., Ostashewski, N., Mishra, M., Gauvreau, S., & Richardson, G. (2017). TEL MOOC Participant Response to the Community of Inquiry Theoretical Framework, *Presentation*

at the ICDE World Conference on Online Learning, 16-19 October 2017 Toronto, Canada.

Retrieved from

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/utq9oiypcf24qrc/Tel%20MOOC%20Participant%20Response%20To.pdf?dl=0>

63. Ostaszewski, N., Cleveland-Innes, M. & Mishra, S. (2017). Technology professional development delivered online: The TEL MOOC Instructional Approach. In J. Dron & S. Mishra (Eds.), *Proceedings of E-Learn: World Conference on E-Learning in Corporate, Government, Healthcare, and Higher Education* (pp. 432-436). Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/181214/>
64. Mishra, S. (2017). Promoting Use and Contribution of Open Educational Resources. *Presented at the Pre-Conference Symposium of the 2017 E-Learn - World Conference on E-Learning, 17 October 2017, Vancouver, Canada*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2800>
65. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2017). From Policy to Practice: Lessons from the Commonwealth. *Presented at the International Forum on ICT and Education 2030, 10 July 2017, Qingdao, China*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2759>
66. Kanwar, A., Balasubramanian, K., & Mishra, S. (2017). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Pacific OER Regional Consultation, 29 May 2017, Auckland, New Zealand*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2743>
67. Mishra, S. (2017). Open Educational Resources at USP: SWOT Analysis. *Presented at the Institutional Policy Development Workshop on Open Educational Resources, The University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji, on 25 May 2017*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2746>
68. Kanwar, A., Mishra, S., & Abeywardena, I. (2017). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Latin America and Caribbean Open Educational Resources Regional Conference, 3 April 2017, Sao Paulo, Brazil*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2728>
69. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2017). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Africa Open Educational Resources Regional Consultation, 2 March 2017, Port Louis, Mauritius*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2714>
70. Kanwar, A., Mishra, S., & Lesperance, J. (2017). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Middle East and North Africa Open Educational Resources Regional Conference, 27 February 2017, Doha, Qatar*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2711>
71. Kanwar, A., Mishra, S., & Venkataraman, B. (2017). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Europe Open Educational Resources Regional Conference, 23 February 2017, Valletta, Malta*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2710>
72. Mishra, S. (2017). Higher education faculty perceptions of quality of Open Educational Resources in India. *Presented at OEGlobal 2017, 8-10 March 2017, Cape Town, South Africa*. Retrieved from <https://conference.oeconsortium.org/2017/presentation/higher-education-faculty-perceptions-of-quality-of-open-educational-resources-in-india/>
73. Kanwar, A., Mishra, S., & Abeywardena, I. (2016). OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action. *Presented at the Asia Regional Consultation on Open Educational Resources, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 1 December 2016*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2785>
74. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2016). Can ODL reach the unreached? Lessons from the Commonwealth. *Keynote delivered at National Open University of Nigeria's Distinguished Lecture Series in Abuja, Nigeria, 27 July 2016*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2378>

75. Mishra, S. (2016). Defining Open Educational Resources (OER) Indicators for National Adoption and Impact. *Presented at the Expert Meeting on developing indicators for OER at UNESCO, Paris, 15 November 2016*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2688>
76. Gaba, A., Mishra, S. (2016). Skill Development through MOOC for Inclusive and Sustainable Development: A Review of Policies in the Asian Commonwealth Countries, *Paper presented at the Pan Commonwealth Forum on Open Learning (PCF8) at Kuala Lumpur from 27-30 November 2016*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2560>
77. Mishra, S. (2016). Mainstreaming Use and Adaptation of Open Educational Resources in Indian Higher Education: A Model. *Poster presented at the 8th Pan-Commonwealth Forum on Open Learning, Kuala Lumpur*. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2671>
78. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2015). A New Paradigm for Open Universities. *Keynote delivered at the AAOU 29th Annual Conference in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia on 1 December 2015*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1760>
79. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2015). The impact of OER and MOOCs on ODL: an international perspective. *Presented at the Centre for Research in Distance Education, Beijing Normal University, China, 10 October 2015*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1734>
80. Kanwar, A., & Mishra, S. (2015). The impact of OER and MOOCs on ODL: an international perspective. *Keynote Address at the 2015 International Distance Education Development Forum, Peking University, Beijing, China, 10 October 2015*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1735>
81. Kanwar, A., Gatsha, G., & Mishra, S. (2015). Widening Access to Education in the Commonwealth: what have we learned? *Keynote address presented at the Distance Education Association of Southern Africa (DEASA) Conference on 18 September 2015 held at the Institute of Distance Education, University of Swaziland*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/1705>
82. Kanwar, A., Cheng, R., & Mishra, S. (2015). OER 2012: Paris and After. *Inaugural address at CEMBA/MPA Meeting of Partners organised in collaboration with the Open University of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka, 23 March 2015*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/774>
83. Kanwar, A., Gatsha, G., Mishra, S., & Lesperance, J. (2015). Advancing Research in Commonwealth Africa: Some Reflections. *Presented at the Commonwealth Tertiary Education Facility (CTEF), Malaysia, 12 February 2015*. Retrieved from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/770>
84. Mishra, S., & Sharma, R. C. (2015). Teachers' Perception of Open Educational Resources: Data Collection through Workshops (ROER4D). *Presented at the Open Education Global Conference (Research Track), 22-24 April 2015. Banff, Canada*. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/oeconsortium/teachers-perception-of-open-educational-resources-data-collection-through-workshops-roer4d?ref=http://roer4d.org/sp-3-teachers-attitude-towards-oer>

Annex 3: List of Workshops Conducted by Dr Sanjaya Mishra at COL

1. Workshop on TEL Benchmarking at the Pan Commonwealth Forum on Open Learning (PCF11) in Gaborone on September 11, 2025.
2. Workshop on Developing Case Studies for Influence and Impact in Gaborone on September 9, 2025.
3. Regional Consultation Workshop on Credit Transfer Framework for Micro-credential at Asia e University, Malaysia from 14-15, 2025.
4. Workshop on Validation of the Policy Guidelines on AI in Higher Education in Mauritius held on April 10, 2025.
5. National Consultation on ICT in Education Policy for Fiji held on March 13, 2025.
6. Training of Trainers workshop on Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action held in Fiji from March 10-12, 2025.
7. Training of trainers' workshop on Open Educational Resources in Mauritius from June 5-7, 2023.
8. Workshop on Blended Learning Design and Open Educational Resources at National Institute of Education, Maldives from 29-31 May 2023.
9. 2nd global consultation meeting of the Small Island Developing States held at UNESCO, Paris from 4-5 April 2023.
10. Asia Regional Focal Point meeting held in New Delhi from 27-28 December 2022.
11. Workshop on development of Policy guidelines for Technology-Enabled Learning at Higher Education Commission, Mauritius from June 1-2, 2022.
12. National Consultation Workshop on Open Educational Resources Policy for Mauritius on May 30, 2022.
13. Workshop on revision of CEMBA/CEMPA Course held at Open University of Mauritius on May 26, 2022.
14. High-level Panel Meeting on Climate Change in Education held in Seychelles on May 23, 2022.
15. Workshop on Open Educational Resources at the Ministry of Education, Seychelles from May 20-22, 2022.
16. Open Educational Resources policy development workshop at Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Open University, Ahmedabad, India from 12-13 December 2019.
17. Stakeholder Consultation workshop on development of Open Educational Resource Strategy for Zambia held on November 28, 2019.
18. Workshop on Policy Development for Technology-Enabled Learning at Kaimosi Friends University College, Kenya from 25-26 November 2019.
19. Workshop on Development of Policy for Implementation of Technology-Enabled Learning at University of Papua New Guinea from March 14-15, 2019.
20. Asia regional Focal Point meeting of COL held in New Delhi from December 10-11, 2018.
21. Training of Trainers (TOT) workshop for the Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action (C-DELTA) held in New Delhi, India from December 5-7, 2018.
22. Workshop on development of Policy for Technology-Enabled Learning at Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Bondo, Kenya from 24-25 September 2018.
23. Workshop for adoption of Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action (C-DELTA) in Antigua and Barbuda from 31 May to 1 June 2018.
24. Workshop for adoption of Commonwealth Digital Education Leadership Training in Action (C-DELTA) in St Lucia from 28-30 May 2018.
25. Workshop on Blended Learning Design at Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge technologies, RK Valley, India from 27-28 March 2018.
26. Workshop on Policy Development for Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at Universiti Malaysia Sabah from 19-20 March 2018.
27. Workshop on Course Writers of CEMBA programme at the Open University of Mauritius on November 14, 2017.

28. Workshop on Sustainable Business as Open Educational Resources at Open University of Mauritius on November 13, 2017.
29. Workshop on Advanced ICT course development at University of Mauritius on November 9-10, 2017.
30. Workshop on Policy Development for Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation at Uganda Management Institute from 6-7 November 2017.
31. Workshop on Open Educational Resources Course Development at University of South Pacific from August 29-30, 2017.
32. Workshop on TEL policy development at National University of Samoa from May 22-23, 2017.
33. Workshop on Open Educational Resources Policy Development at University of South Pacific on May 25, 2017.
34. UNESCO expert meeting on developing Indicators for Open Educational Resources Adoption held in Paris, France from 4-5 April 2017.
35. Africa regional workshop on Open Educational Resources held in Port Louis, Mauritius from March 2-3, 2017.
36. Workshop on Cape Town Open Education Declaration organised by Open Education Consortium at Cape Town, South Africa on March 7, 2017.
37. Workshop on development of Policy for Technology-Enabled Learning at Rajiv Gandhi University Knowledge Technologies, India on March 15, 2017.
38. National Consultation Workshop on Open Educational Resources for Malaysia held in Kuala Lumpur from 24-25 November 2016.
39. National Consultation Workshop on Open Educational Resources for Bangladesh, held in Dhaka on 19 November 2016.
40. Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Massive Open Online Courses held at Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia from 2-3 May 2016.
41. Workshop on development of Policy for Technology-Enabled Learning at SNDT Women's University, India from 25-26 April 2016.
42. Workshop on developing OER Roadmap held at UNESCO, Paris from 30-31 March 2016.
43. Workshop on Open Educational Resources Policy Development at the Open University of Tanzania on January 28, 2016.
44. The Caribbean regional Open Textbook Forum held at Antigua & Barbuda from 26-28 October 2015.
45. Regional workshop on Commonwealth Certificate for Teacher ICT Integration held in South Africa from 25-26 May 2015.

Annex 4: Selected COL Activity Related Publications of Dr Sanjaya Mishra

Books

1. Isaacs, S., & Mishra, S. (2022). *Smart education strategies for teaching and learning: Critical analytical framework and case studies*. UNESCO IITE. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/4464>
2. Mishra, S., & Zholdoshalieva, R. (eds). (2021). *Guidelines on open and distance learning for youth and adult literacy*. UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning and COL. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379397>
3. Mishra, S., and Panda, S. (eds). (2020). *Technology-enabled learning: Policy, pedagogy and practice*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3655>
4. Miao, F., Mishra, S., Orr, D., & Janssen, B. (2019). *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies*. UNESCO & COL. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>
5. Sankey, M., & Mishra, S. (2019). *Benchmarking toolkit for technology-enabled learning*, Commonwealth of Learning. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/3217>
6. Mishra, S. (2017). *Promoting use and contribution of open educational resources*. CEMCA. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2659>
7. Miao, F., Mishra, S., & McGreal, R. (eds). (2016). *Open educational resources: Policy, costs and transformation*, COL and UNESCO. <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2306>

Book Chapters

1. Karunanayaka, S.P., & Mishra, S. (2025). Teacher Capacity Development in Digital Education in Sri Lanka through an Innovative Platform. In B. Ogange, M. Newmann, & T. Mays (Eds). *Innovative Models and Practices in Teacher Development: Case Studies from the Commonwealth*. (pp.82-96). Commonwealth of Learning.
2. Mishra, S., & Panda, S. (2020). Prologue: Setting the stage for technology-enabled learning. In S. Mishra & S. Panda (eds). *Technology-enabled learning: Policy, pedagogy and practice* (pp. 3-16). Commonwealth of Learning.
3. Mishra, S. (2020). Technology applications in education: Policy and prospects. In S. Mishra & S. Panda (eds). *Technology-enabled learning: Policy, pedagogy and practice* (pp. 19-31). Commonwealth of Learning.
4. Mishra, S., & Panigrahi, M.R. (2020). Developing institutional capacities for OER-based eLearning. In S. Mishra & S. Panda (eds). *Technology-enabled learning: Policy, pedagogy and practice* (pp. 109-116). Commonwealth of Learning.
5. Mishra, S., & Panda, S. (2020). Epilogue: Towards mainstreaming technology-enabled learning. In S. Mishra & S. Panda (eds). *Technology-enabled learning: Policy, pedagogy and practice* (pp. 3-16). Commonwealth of Learning.
6. Mishra, S., Cleveland-Innes, M., & Ostashewski, N. (2020). A Case Study of the Technology-Enabled Learning (TEL) Massive Open Online Courses, In K. Zhang, C. J. Bonk, T. C. Reeves, & T. H. Reynolds. *MOOCs and Open Education in the Global South: Challenges, Successes, and Opportunities*. (pp.156-168). Routledge.

Journal Papers

1. Mishra, S., Jha, N.K., & Bhagat, K.K. (2025). Review and validation of the benchmarking of technology-enabled learning. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 12(3), 450-468. <https://doi.org/10.56059/jl4d.v12i3.2410>

2. Mishra, S. (2025). Evaluating capacity building for blended learning in the Commonwealth. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies Trends & Practices*, 15(2), 277-297.
<https://doi.org/10.52634/mier/2025/v15/i2/3162>
3. Mishra, S. (2025). Can online learning be scaled using a frugal approach? *Journal of Open, Distance, and Digital Education*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.25619/qy1tsg74>
4. Bhagat, K. K., Mishra, S., & Wang, T. (2025). Blended learning in Commonwealth countries: a comparative analysis of implementation and impact. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 1-31.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-025-00356-z>
5. Ally, M., & Mishra, S. (2024). Policies for artificial intelligence in higher education: A call for action. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*, 50(3), 1-12.
<https://doi.org/10.21432/cjlt28869>
6. Mishra, S. (2019). Early years of the *Journal of Learning for Development*: A combination of bibliometrics and thematic analysis, *Journal of Learning for Development*, 6(2), 160-176.
<https://jl4d.org/index.php/ejl4d/article/view/331/393>
7. Cleveland-Innes, M., Gauvreau, S., Richardson, G., Mishra, S., & Ostashewski, N. (2019). Technology-enabled learning and the benefits and challenges of using the community of inquiry theoretical framework, *International Journal of E-Learning and Distance Education*, 34(1),
<http://www.ijede.ca/index.php/jde/article/view/1108>
8. Mishra, S., Sharma, M., Sharma, R. C., Singh, A. & Thakur, A. (2016). Development of a scale to measure faculty attitude towards open educational resources. *Open Praxis*, 8(1).
<http://openpraxis.org/index.php/OpenPraxis/article/view/236>

Annex 5: Institutions Supported

I worked closely with colleagues in the following institutions/organizations:

1. Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh
2. Allama Iqbal Open University, Pakistan
3. Alupe University, Kenya
4. Antigua State College, Antigua and Barbuda
5. Athabasca University, Canada
6. Bangladesh Open University
7. Centurion University of Technology and Management, India
8. Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
9. Dhaka Ahsania Mission, Bangladesh
10. Digital Empowerment Foundation, India
11. Fiji National University
12. Griffith University, Australia
13. Higher Education Commission, Mauritius
14. Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
15. Indira Gandhi National Open University, India
16. International Islamic University Malaysia
17. Islamic University of Maldives
18. Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Kenya
19. Kaimosi Friends University College, Kenya
20. KampaBits, Uganda
21. Kibabii University, Kenya
22. Mahatma Gandhi Institute, Mauritius
23. Makerere University, Uganda
24. Mauritius Institute of Education
25. Mauritius Institute of Training Development
26. Model Institute of Education and Research, India
27. Nakuru Training Institute, Kenya
28. National Institute of Education, Maldives
29. National Open University of Nigeria
30. National University of Samoa
31. Odisha State Open University, India
32. Open University Malaysia
33. Open University of Mauritius
34. Open University of Sri Lanka
35. Open University of Tanzania
36. Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, India
37. SchoolNet South Africa
38. Seychelles Institute of Distance and Open Learning
39. SNDT Women's University, India
40. Uganda Management Institute
41. Université des Mascareignes, Mauritius
42. Universiti Malaysia Sabah
43. Universiti Sains Malaysia

44. University of Cape Town, South Africa
45. University of Kabianga, Kenya
46. University of Mauritius
47. University of Papua New Guinea
48. University of South Pacific
49. University of Technology, Mauritius
50. University of the Bahamas
51. University Sains Islam Malaysia

End Notes

¹ Kirkwood, A., Price, L. (2016). *Technology-Enabled Learning Implementation Handbook*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2363>

² <https://cdelta.col.org/>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TshhZUEjZhg&list=PLXN-JCVb8z8BFwDIIiBiCIJh3fOXLEckEO>

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HWnYUvKV5NQ>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0LeeOuQx-w&list=PLXN-JCVb8z8DT7yF4Xz03P5F3qXqHq8Mz>

⁶ <https://colcommons.org/>

⁷ A tripod metaphor is often used for this model as a tripod is considered to be more stable.

⁸ Bhagat, K.K. (2025). *Technology-Enabled Learning in the Commonwealth Countries: A Research Synthesis*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5696>

⁹ Cleveland-Innes, M., & Wilton, D. (2018). *Guide to Blended Learning*. Commonwealth of Learning. <https://doi.org/10.56059/11599/3095>

¹⁰ Ally, M., & Mishra, S. (2024). *Developing Policy Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence in Post-secondary Institutions*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/5615>

¹¹ Perryman, L-A. (2020). *TEL MOOC long-term impact evaluation study*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3482>

¹² Ostashewski, N., & Cleveland-Innes, M. (2022). *Participant Experience in an Inquiry-Based Massive Open Online Course*. Commonwealth of Learning. <https://doi.org/10.56059/11599/4132>

¹³ Advanced ICT Skills Development Project. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/2925>

¹⁴ Internal reflection report submitted by the Education Specialist for the Meta-evaluation of the Strategic Plan 2015-2021. The estimate used the methodology adopted by SPARC, USA in estimating the value of OER (see <https://sparcopen.org/news/2018/estimating-oer-student-savings/>)

¹⁵ Gaeta, N., & Bustamante, N. (2019). *ICT for Youth Employability: Evaluation Report*. Commonwealth of Learning. <http://hdl.handle.net/11599/3199>

Views expressed are personal. The information on this document is not an official opinion of the Commonwealth of Learning. I have not included several activities and events in this reflection report. While the presentation is selective, I may also have missed highlighting some important achievements.

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